

Scalability of Hemp-based Thermal Insulation in the United States – A Monte Carlo-based Techno-economic Approach

1. Abstract

Decarbonizing the construction sector is vital to meet the greenhouse gas emission targets. To this end, the development and deployment of bio-based alternatives to existing construction materials is becoming an increasingly used strategy to reduce the embodied carbon of the built environment. Hemp-based insulation is one such alternative. This study proposes a Monte Carlo-based techno-economic model to fill this gap. The developed model incorporates the uncertainty surrounding a supply chain in its infancy to determine the economic viability of the hemp insulation across a range of input parameters. The results obtained show that the retrofit of existing bioproducts/manufacturing plants to produce hemp insulation increases the rate of payback and decreases the breakeven revenue. The model further analyzes the economic viability of hemp insulation across different production rates and selling prices, which in turn reflects economic performance across different rates of demand and market penetration. Further sensitivity analysis shows that the price of the procured hemp fibers, the selling price of the finished product, and the demand for the finished product are key factors that determine the magnitude of economic success.

2. Objective

- Develop and deploy a Monte-Carlo-based techno-economic model for hemp insulation, including uncertainties surrounding the various cost elements and market for the product.
- Use scenario analysis to investigate the techno-economic viability based on the level of capital expenditure required—alterations to an existing bioproducts/insulation manufacturing plant versus building a new plant.
- Test the model for convergence, replicability, and perform sensitivity analyses to reveal robust metrics including the probability of the positive net present value (NPV), breakeven revenue, and payback period

3. Methodology

Flow diagram of Monte Carlo-based techno-economic model

4. Results

Probability of Positive NPV

Morris Sensitivity Analysis (where the plot on the left is the relationship between the mean and standard deviation and the plot on the right is the ranking of the means)

Hemp Batt Insulation